

A method for rearing armyworm *Spodoptera mauritia acronyctoides* Guenée (Lepidoptera:Noctuidae) on graminaceous hosts

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Armyworms often are reared in petri dishes with moistened paper towel and cut rice leaves to track development of individuals. But this method entails changing of plants and removing fecal material daily and is unreliable. Also larval survival is low because of high levels of fungal or bacterial infections. We have designed a setup to minimize these disadvantages (see figure). One-month-old host plants are uprooted. Individual tillers are separated, wrapped with moistened cotton, and placed in 10.5- × 2.5-cm test tubes. A cardboard plug prevents larvae from drowning. Each test tube with plant is enclosed in a 19- × 4-cm cylindrical mylar cage with nylon mesh vents on the side and top. Nylon mesh attached to the base of the cylinder traps fecal material and aerates it to prevent fungal or bacterial infection. One first-instar larva is placed on each host plant, using a moist camelhair brush. Caged plants with larvae are held upright in a wooden rack. (We used a compartmentalized 47- × 85-cm seedbox to accommodate 60 setups.). Plants are replaced every 3 d. Average pupation of *S. m. acronyctoides* larvae was higher with this method than with using petri dishes (see table).

Pupation of <i>Spodoptera mauritia acronyctoides</i> reared on graminaceous host plants. IRRI laboratory and greenhouse, June-July 1988.		
Plant	Pupation (%) ^a /	
	Petri dish method	Whole plant method
<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	0	100 ±0
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i> Munro ex Hook f	20 ±0.45	100 ±0
<i>E. colona</i> (L.) Link	40 ±0.55	100 ±0
<i>Brachiaria distachya</i> (L.) Stapf.	20 ±0.45	80 ±0.45
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) Beauv. ssp. <i>hispidula</i> (Retz.) Honda	40 ±0.55	80 ±0.45
<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i> Berg.	40 ±0.55	80 ±0.45
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i> (L.) Nees	20 ±0.45	60 ±0.55
Mean	26 ±0.15	86 ±0.15
^a / Av of 5 replications.		

Catindig, J.L.A., Barrion, A.T., and Litsinger, J.A. 1989. A method for rearing armyworm *Spodoptera mauritia acronyctoides* Guene (Lepidoptera:Noctuidae) on graminaceous hosts. Int. Rice Res. Newsl. 14(3):39